

An Iterative Network Flow Algorithm for Online Pickup and Delivery

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Abstract. The pickup and delivery problem optimizes the routing of vehicles to transport goods between origin and destination locations with a limited fleet. These routing decisions aim to satisfy demand while minimizing empty miles for vehicle rebalancing between customers and for vehicle repositioning toward satisfying future demand. This paper addresses two common difficulties: large numbers of vehicles and limited information regarding future demand. We formalize a new variant of the online pickup and delivery problem with batched demand, no demand backlog, and a distance minimization objective. We then show that the offline problem is equivalent to a—polynomially solvable—network flow reformulation in a high-vehicle regime, under a balancing condition requiring that both the vehicles’ starting and ending locations cover all nodes. We then embed the network flow problem into a polynomial-time online algorithm for the online pickup and delivery problem. We then develop a polynomial-time strengthened online algorithm that still relies on the network flow algorithm but avoids unnecessary empty miles by postponing unnecessary edges at the end of each period. We show that these algorithms are asymptotically 2-competitive, whereas a myopic integer programming baseline is not c -competitive for any $c > 0$. Computational experiments show that the online algorithm returns high-quality solutions in less than a thousandth of the runtime of an integer programming benchmark.

Key words: network flow, vehicle routing, online optimization, pickup and delivery, approximation algorithms

1. Introduction

Transportation and logistics are essential to moving people and goods, yet limited margins and ambitious decarbonization targets create mounting pressure to enhance operating efficiency and, in particular, to mitigate empty miles. The pickup and delivery problem optimizes the routing of goods from origin to destination with a limited fleet of vehicles (Savelsbergh and Sol 1995). This paper focuses on full truckload (FTL) operations, in which each unit of demand materializes in a unit truckload—a segment contributing to nearly half of the \$900B American trucking industry. In such settings, routing decisions are important to control how many empty miles are incurred to rebalance vehicles between customer-serving trips and to reposition vehicles for future demand.

The FTL pickup and delivery problem is NP-hard and notoriously challenging to solve via integer-programming methods (Dumas et al. 1991, Savelsbergh and Sol 1995). This paper addresses two core challenges: (i) the computational complexity arising from a large number of vehicles, and (ii) the uncertainty regarding future demand. In response to the first challenge, we develop a computationally efficient procedure with guarantees on solution quality and good practical performance. In response to the second, we ensure that vehicle ending locations remain relatively balanced across the network, which is important for supporting future online routing operations.

1.1. Literature Review

There is a wealth of literature on the pickup and delivery problem (see Savelsbergh and Sol (1995) for an overview) and related problems.

Offline Pickup and Delivery Problem (OffPDP) The OffPDP optimizes routing operations to serve demand requests. It extends the traditional VRP framework by additionally accommodating the precedence and pairing constraints of pickup and delivery (Dumas et al. 1991). It is typically

solved via integer optimization techniques, such as branch-and-cut (Cordeau and Laporte 2007), column generation (Baldacci et al. 2011a,b) and branch-and-price (Ropke and Cordeau 2009, Cherkesly et al. 2015). These algorithms scale to instances with on the order of a hundred customers. To combat the computational complexity on larger instances, heuristic algorithms have also been applied to the OffPDP, including tabu search (Gendreau et al. 1999, Cordeau and Laporte 2003) and local search (Renaud et al. 2002). Recent papers use network representations of OffPDP, such as shareability networks (Alonso-Mora et al. 2017), request-compatibility networks (Bertsimas et al. 2019), or subpath-based networks characterizing sequences of pickups and dropoffs (Alyasiry et al. 2019, Martin-Iradi et al. 2024, Rist and Forbes 2021, Zhang et al. 2023).

The problem has also been studied via approximation algorithms. Notably, Frederickson et al. (1978) derived a 9/5-approximation. Our paper takes a different approach by identifying a subclass of OffPDP problems that can be solved in polynomial time via a network flow representation. Unlike request-compatibility/shareability networks, which encode pairs or sequences of feasible choices in a *newly constructed* graph, we propose in this paper a novel construction that yields an exact min-cost flow formulation on the *original* graph (and therefore admits a polynomial-time algorithm via linear relaxation). We obtain this result in a high-vehicle regime, with at least as many vehicles as nodes. This structure is then leveraged for the online setting, where the same balanced subproblem is solved repeatedly as demand is revealed over time.

Online Pickup and Delivery Problem (OnPDP) The OnPDP falls into the broader literature on online routing (Berbeglia et al. 2010, Fleischmann et al. 2004). Most theoretical studies consider settings with demand backlog and makespan-minimization objectives, rather than batched demand with no backlog and a cost-minimization objective. This is because a cost-minimization problem would not be salient in a setting with a demand backlog. In such a makespan-minimization setting, approximation ratios of 2 and $(2+\epsilon)$ have been shown to exist for the online Euclidean VRP (Jaillet and Wagner 2008a,b). For the OnPDP, Ascheuer et al. (2000) devised a 2-competitive algorithm for the closed-tour version (i.e., when vehicles return to the depot). In the single-server case, Feuerstein and Stougie (2001) derived a lower bound of 2 for any deterministic online algorithm. In the open-tour version, the best known lower bound is 2.0585 (Birn et al. 2023) and the best known upper bound is $1 + \phi \approx 2.618$ (Baligács et al. 2022). These upper-bounding algorithms are themselves non-polynomial, by solving NP-hard PDP instances repeatedly. By contrast, our setting requires all demand in each batch to be served within the period, making vehicle positioning central to future performance, and also disallowing the possibility of waiting until all requests have materialized and then making routing decisions afterwards.

A separate stream of literature has developed computational algorithms for online routing problems (Psaraftis 1995). Online versions of these problems involve dynamically handling requests as they arrive, optimizing routes in real-time. Algorithms based on reinforcement learning have been proposed to address the dynamic nature of these problems and achieve competitive performance compared to offline approaches (James et al. 2019). More recently, Bertsimas et al. (2019) had success integrating mixed-integer programming methods with rolling-horizon and other heuristics to solve the online vehicle routing problem at scale. Approximate dynamic programming and reinforcement learning methods aim to solve sequential routing problems under uncertainty (see, e.g., Ulmer (2017), James et al. (2019) in routing, Maxwell et al. (2010) in ambulance deployment, Shah et al. (2020), Azagirre et al. (2024) in ride-sharing, Goodson et al. (2016) in distribution systems). Variations of the OnPDP in the literature studied via computational algorithms include the dial-a-ride problem and the dynamic stacker crane problem (Berbeglia et al. 2010).

Our paper contributes a new online PDP setting with demand uncertainty but no backlog, meaning that the operator must serve all demand in each timestep. Unlike the backlog-based,

makespan-minimization settings more commonly studied in the literature, our setting uses a cost-minimization objective and measures performance by total distance traveled over time. We devise polynomial-time algorithms, prove that they are asymptotically 2-competitive, and report computational results showing that they can return high-quality solutions orders of magnitude faster than integer programming benchmarks.

Related work in transportation operations has also imposed vehicle availability or reserve constraints for different locations as a proxy for future operational readiness (Gopalan and Talluri 1998, Hemmelmayr et al. 2013, Rahimi-Vahed et al. 2015, Birolini and Jacquillat 2023, Jacquillat and Lo 2024). Our paper differs by formalizing this idea directly within an online pickup-and-delivery framework and using it to establish entirely new algorithms.

1.2. Contributions

This paper develops polynomial-time algorithms and theoretical performance guarantees for offline and online pickup and delivery problems (OffPDP and OnPDP). We consider a setting with batched demand and no backlog, meaning that customer requests arise sequentially and must be served before the following batch. This setting is practically relevant because the optimizer must not only serve current demand, but also leave the fleet in locations that can serve the next batch efficiently. In addition, this allows us to study the natural minimum distance objective, as it rules out the otherwise trivial method of waiting for all requests to be revealed and then optimizing routing decisions afterwards. We also consider a regime with a large number of vehicles—at least as many as the number of nodes in the network. This setup corresponds, for instance, to large regional companies with a limited number of facilities but large flows between these locations. In this setting, the key challenge is to serve current demand efficiently while preserving enough spatial coverage of the fleet to handle future demand efficiently, no matter what that future demand materializes to be.

Specifically, this paper employs a graph-theoretic methodology to solve the OffPDP and OnPDP problems. Its first contribution is to develop a network-flow equivalence for the OffPDP problem under the assumption that at least one vehicle starts in each node and under the additional constraint that at least one vehicle ends in each node (referred to as the balanced offline PDP problem, or OffPDP-B). In this setting, we prove that a network flow formulation can solve the OffPDP problem to optimality. The proof proceeds by combining the vehicle paths in an optimal OffPDP-B solution to form Eulerian tours, which we use to obtain the set of least-cost edge flows ensuring a balanced end state with at least one vehicle per node. This equivalence result yields a polynomial-time algorithm for the OffPDP-B, which exhibits much stronger scalability than integer programming benchmarks.

By maintaining at least one vehicle per node, the OffPDP-B can be solved repeatedly in an online fashion. Our second contribution is to show that this online algorithm achieves an asymptotic competitive ratio of 2 in the OnPDP, as the time horizon grows indefinitely. To our knowledge, this result provides the first theoretical guarantees on the competitive ratio for the OnPDP problem with batched demand and no backlog. This contrast highlights that preserving fleet coverage is not only a practical consideration but also a key ingredient for reducing long-run cost. Importantly, these performance guarantees are information-agnostic to the demand distribution—in particular, they hold in the absence of good data or good predictions. To underscore the significance of this result, we show that a myopic benchmark, which solves the OffPDP at each iteration without constraining the number of ending vehicles per node, can return arbitrarily large costs as compared to our online algorithm and to the hindsight optimum.

From a practical standpoint, one downside of the online algorithm is that it can induce empty miles for rebalancing purposes—to merely satisfy the constraint that at least one vehicle ends in

each location. The third contribution of this paper is to develop a strengthened online algorithm that still relies on the network flow algorithm at each iteration but avoids unnecessary empty miles. Specifically, the strengthening procedure postpones unnecessary edges to replace empty rebalancing trips at the end of the current period by demand-carrying trips at the beginning of the subsequent period. The main challenge is to do this without destroying the structural conditions needed to guarantee that the graph can still be decomposed into routes for the individual vehicles to traverse. This is done by partitioning the network flow into vehicle paths, and then partitioning each vehicle path into an initial segment that aligns the starting state, a middle segment that serves the current-period route, and a final segment of rebalancing edges that can be postponed to the next period. We prove that this strengthened online algorithm is still polynomially solvable and returns a solution at least as strong as the original one—thereby also achieving a competitive ratio of 2.

The last contribution of the paper is to demonstrate the scalability and practical performance of the offline and online algorithms. We first show that the network flow algorithm returns the optimal solution for the OffPDP-B problem several orders of magnitude faster than integer programming benchmarks. We then show that the online network flow-based algorithms achieve similar performance to an integer programming benchmark for the OnPDP problem but in less than a thousandth of the runtime on small instances with up to 10 nodes. Moreover, the integer programming benchmark fails to scale to medium- and large-sized instances, whereas our network flow-based algorithm still terminates in seconds with hundreds of nodes and in minutes with thousands of nodes. Altogether, this paper identifies a class of pickup and delivery problems that can be solved effectively using simple network flow representations, yielding polynomial-time algorithms that can scale effectively to large instances and to online decision-making environments.

2. Problem Statement

2.1. The Offline Pickup and Delivery Problem (OffPDP)

The OffPDP takes as inputs a directed graph with arc costs, a set of full-truckload demand requests, and a set of vehicles each associated with a starting location and a target ending location. It optimizes the route of each vehicle to serve all demand requests while minimizing travel costs. This offline problem serves as the building block for the online model introduced in Subsection 2.2.

Mathematically, let $G(V, E)$ be a complete directed graph with n nodes. Each edge (i, j) is associated with unit cost c_{ij} and demand d_{ij} . We denote by m the number of vehicles, and by $S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m\}$ and $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$ the multisets of starting and ending locations, respectively. The problem seeks m directed paths, stored in $P := \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_m\}$, allowing for cycles and empty paths. The set P is said to cover demand if the number of directed edges from i to j across P_1, P_2, \dots, P_m is at least d_{ij} . We refer to as $PDP(G, S, T, C, D)$ the set of paths in graph G of least cost (given by C) that cover demand (given by D) with vehicles starting in locations in S and ending in locations in T . We also denote by $PDP(G, S, -, C, D)$ the variant with no requirement on ending locations. When inputs are clear, we refer to the OffPDP problem for convenience.

The model relies on the following standard FTL assumptions:

- All vehicles are homogeneous and incur the same cost. This assumption allows us to leverage symmetry across paths by taking permutations of vehicles traveling along the same paths.
- The cost matrix satisfies the strict triangle inequality, i.e., $c_{ij} + c_{jk} > c_{ik}$ for distinct i, j, k .
- The cost matrix is symmetric, i.e., $c_{ij} = c_{ji}$ for distinct i, j .
- Each demand request must be served but there are no time windows. In turn, the cost of a route is the sum of the costs of the edges, and does not incorporate level-of-service components.
- Each demand request utilizes a full truckload, so each vehicle has unit capacity. As a result, we can assume without loss of generality that each request travels directly from origin to destination, per the triangle inequality and full-truckload assumptions.

2.2. The Online Pickup and Delivery Problem (OnPDP)

The OnPDP defines a sequential pickup and delivery problem under demand uncertainty. At each timestep/time period, a new batch of demand requests is revealed and must be served before the next time period. The interdependencies between time periods lie in the locations of the vehicles—the ending locations at each time period define the starting locations in the next time period. Therefore, routing decisions affect not only current operating cost, but also the fleet’s readiness for future demand.

This OnPDP problem departs from some earlier models in the literature via the treatment of the demand and the objective function. Specifically, our problem considers batched demand with no backlog and a cost minimization objective, as opposed to a setting with demand backlog and a makespan minimization objective. This setting captures a practical setting where demand requests need to be served within a particular time period (e.g., a day, a week) but the operator can strategically route its vehicles to be best positioned for the next batch.

Let $S^0 \in V^m$ denote the starting locations of the vehicles, and D_{ij}^t be the demand from node i to node j in timestep $t = 1, \dots, \tau$. Without loss of generality, we assume throughout this paper that there exists $(i, j) \in E$ such that $D_{ij}^t > 0$ for all $t = 1, \dots, \tau$. At each timestep t , we seek a solution to the offline problem $PDP(G, S^t, -, C, D^t)$, with starting locations S^t , costs C , and demand D^t .

Alternatively, we can define the decision as the combination of the ending locations of the vehicles and the resulting paths of the vehicles. Under this alternative representation, the decisions include both $T^t \in V^m$ and the solution to the offline problem $PDP(G, S^t, T^t, C, D^t)$.

This OnPDP problem can be cast as a dynamic program over a finite horizon $t = 1, \dots, \tau$. The state variable is the set $S^t \in V^m$ of starting locations and the realized demand encapsulated in the matrix D^t . The decision is the set of m ending locations $T^t \in V^m$ and the resulting paths for the vehicles that start in the locations given in S^t , end in the locations given in T^t , and cover the demand in D^t . The transition function defines the starting locations at time $t + 1$ as the ending locations at time t , and generates the demand matrix D^{t+1} from an unknown probability distribution. The cost per period is equal to the arc costs summed over the m vehicle paths, denoted by $c(u^t)$.

Let $J_t(S^t, D^t)$ denote the cost-to-go function at time t . The Bellman equation is given as follows, where the expectation is taken over the unknown demand distribution:

$$J_{\tau+1}(S^{\tau+1}, D^{\tau+1}) = 0; \quad J_t(S^t, D^t) = \min_{T^t \in V^m, u^t \in PDP(G, S^t, T^t, C, D^t)} \{c(u^t) + \mathbb{E}J_{t+1}(T^t, D^{t+1})\}$$

This dynamic program combines the complexity of sequential decision-making under uncertainty with that of discrete PDP optimization, and would therefore be highly challenging to solve optimally. Instead, we seek algorithms with bounded competitive ratios in the asymptotic regime where $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, defined as the worst-case ratio between the algorithm’s solution and the hindsight optimum.

DEFINITION 1. An online algorithm is **asymptotically c -competitive** if there exists a constant K such that for any input sequence σ and any time horizon $\tau \geq K$, its cost $C(\sigma, \tau)$ satisfies

$$C(\sigma, \tau) \leq (c + o(1)) \cdot C^*(\sigma, \tau),$$

where $C^*(\sigma, \tau)$ denotes the hindsight-optimal cost on the same input sequence over horizon τ , and where the $o(1)$ term vanishes as $\tau \rightarrow \infty$. The **asymptotic competitive ratio** of the algorithm is the infimum over all c satisfying this property.

Our goal is to design polynomial algorithms with an asymptotic competitive ratio of 2 for the OnPDP. We will propose a rolling-horizon online algorithm that solves an offline PDP instance at each iteration, while ensuring that the ending locations of the vehicles cover all the nodes, so that

incoming demand can be handled effectively in the next time period. This balancing requirement ensures that the algorithm hedges against future demand uncertainty while also allowing for an efficient algorithm. First, we will show that this type of OffPDP instance can be solved in polynomial time, using a network flow equivalence.

3. Network Flow Equivalence for the balanced offline PDP

We consider in this section the balanced offline PDP problem (OffPDP-B), which constrains the ending locations of all vehicles to cover all the nodes in the network. This restriction aims to spread vehicles evenly through the network in order to serve future demand effectively in the OnPDP—as we shall see in the next section, it will yield strong performance guarantees in the OnPDP. Importantly, when the vehicle paths are aggregated into a single graph, it turns out that this structure also allows for an efficient algorithm.

For expositional ease, we assume in the main body that there are *exactly* as many vehicles as nodes in the network, i.e., $m = n$. All results extend to the case where $m > n$, as described in Appendix D (in contrast, we leave the case where $m < n$ out of the scope of this paper). Thus, the OffPDP-B seeks a set of n paths that cover demand, and such that exactly one vehicle starts and ends in each node. With our earlier notation, this corresponds to $PDP(G, \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, D)$.

Consider the following set of demand edges in Figure 1, with costs given by Euclidean distance:

Figure 1 A set of demands for an instance of the PDP.

Here, let each edge represent one unit of demand. In order to obtain a solution to OffPDP-B, we must have a set of six directed paths that covers these edges, each with unique starting points from each other and ending points from each other.

Figure 2 Eulerian tour derived from PDP solution.

It turns out Figure 2 is the optimal solution, where each color represents a path, and we have three empty paths. As seen in Figure 2, the graph sum of the paths forms an Eulerian tour. It turns out that we can solve OffPDP-B by searching for such an Eulerian tour, removing the set of demand edges, and then solving via linear programming. We can now state the main result from this section, which states that the OffPDP-B problem can be solved via a network flow formulation, hence in polynomial time.

THEOREM 1. *The optimal solution of OffPDP-B can be obtained via a network flow formulation.*

The proof of this result is reported in Appendix A.3. We outline the main steps below to provide intuition behind this result. The proof relies at its core on a well-known result on Eulerian tours.

Recall that a directed graph admits an Eulerian tour (a path in a graph that visits every edge of its connected component exactly once and returns to the starting vertex) on each connected component if and only if every node has equal in-degree and out-degree within that component.

CLAIM 1. *Eulerian tours exist on each connected component of a network if and only if the in-degree of each node is equal to its out-degree.*

This concept is useful here because, in OffPDP-B, every vehicle path starts at a unique node and ends at a unique node. As a result, when we take the graph sum of the paths, the path endpoints cancel out, leaving only the imbalance created by demand.

By design, the solution of the OffPDP-B has the same total in-degree and out-degree flow in each node, since one vehicle starts and exactly one vehicle ends in each node. Therefore, we can construct Eulerian tours on each connected component of the graph from the OffPDP-B solution by taking the graph sum of the paths. In other words, once the n vehicle paths are added together, the requirement of one distinct path starting and one distinct path ending at each node creates a canceling-out effect. This implies that feasible OffPDP-B solutions induce Eulerian structure. This is illustrated in Figure 3 and stated in the following lemma.

LEMMA 1. *In each connected component, the graph sum of the paths in any feasible solution of OffPDP-B contains an Eulerian tour.*

Lemma 1 allows us to convert the path-based OffPDP-B formulation to a flow-based formulation. Because the graph sum of the paths is Eulerian on each connected component, the only variables we need to optimize for are the non-demand edges needed to compensate for net demand imbalances. In other words, the routing problem is equivalent to selecting the cheapest rebalancing edges that restore node balance.

Figure 3 Illustration of the Eulerian tour as the graph sum of optimal paths in the OffPDP-B.

Lemma 1 allows us to solve the following network flow formulation to solve the OffPDP-B. The variables x_{ij} represent the number of rebalancing movements from i to j , or in other words the edges in the final solution not including demand edges.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min \quad & \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} \cdot x_{ij} \\
 \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{j \in V} x_{ji} - \sum_{j \in V} x_{ij} = Q_i, \quad \forall i \in V \\
 & x_{ij} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where $Q_i := \sum_{j \in V} d_{ij} - \sum_{j \in V} d_{ji}$ is the net outbound demand at node $i \in V$ (the imbalance that the rebalancing edges seek to offset). This formulation provides the least-cost set of rebalancing (empty-mile) edges to handle demand imbalances in the network. The proof proceeds by showing equivalence in both directions. First, any feasible OffPDP-B solution can be combined into Eulerian tours whose non-demand edges are a feasible solution to Formulation (1). Second, any feasible solution to Formulation (1), after being combined with the demand edges, forms Eulerian components that can then be split into feasible vehicle paths.

LEMMA 2. *OffPDP-B can be solved by solving Formulation (1) and adding all demand edges.*

The proof of Lemma 2 establishes a correspondence between OffPDP-B and Formulation (1). Starting from any feasible OffPDP-B solution, Lemma 1 implies that the graph sum decomposes into Eulerian components; removing the demand edges yields a feasible rebalancing flow. Conversely, we show that the solution to Formulation (1) forms an Eulerian tour on each component, which can be used to construct a corresponding solution in OffPDP-B. These transformations retain the same objective values upon accounting for demand in OffPDP, thus proving that OffPDP-B can be solved via Formulation (1). By construction, Formulation (1) has a network flow structure, so it can be solved via its linear relaxation in polynomial time.

The equivalence in this section relies critically on two features of our problem. First, all demand must be served, so the demand edges are fixed and the only remaining degree of freedom is the rebalancing flow needed to restore balance. Second, the requirement that exactly one path starts and ends at each node creates exactly the symmetry that underlies the Eulerian structure. Due to these structural assumptions, OffPDP-B is exactly equivalent to a network flow problem.

4. A 2-competitive algorithm for the OnPDP

We leverage the network flow solution to OffPDP-B to devise a polynomial 2-competitive algorithm for the OnPDP. To put this result in perspective, we define a myopic baseline that solves the OffPDP at each timestep, without constraining the ending locations of the vehicles. We show that the baseline can perform arbitrarily worse than our algorithm, hence than the hindsight-optimal solution, which underscores the benefits of maintaining a balanced vehicle distribution. The key idea is that paying some rebalancing cost during one timestep can lead to much larger savings in the next timestep by preserving fleet coverage across nodes. Throughout, we still assume that the numbers of vehicles and nodes are equal, which we relax in Appendix D.

4.1. A 2-competitive online algorithm

Algorithm 1 presents the procedure to solve the OnPDP. Because the algorithm solves the balanced offline problem for the realized demand at each time period, the algorithm is feasible by construction: all current demand is served, and the fleet is returned to one vehicle per node for the next period. The algorithm starts by paying a one-time cost to spread the vehicles evenly prior to the first period. Then, at each timestep, the batch of demand requests is revealed and the algorithm solves OffPDP-B via the network flow formulation, thus covering the demand while maintaining one vehicle per node at the beginning of the next timestep.

Algorithm 1 Online algorithm to solve OnPDP

Input: $G(V, E), C, S^0, D^1 \dots D^\tau$ where D^t is available at the start of timestep t

Let x^0 be the matching solution from S^0 to $\{1, \dots, n\}$.

For $t = 1, \dots, \tau$, let x^t be the network flow solution to $PDP(G, \{1, \dots, n\}, \{1, \dots, n\}, C, D^t)$.

Return: x^0, \dots, x^τ

Consider an example (Figure 4) with two nodes A and B , one demand unit from A to B in odd timesteps, and one demand unit from B to A in even timesteps. In odd timesteps, Algorithm 1 moves one vehicle from A to B to serve demand, and one vehicle from B to A for rebalancing. Similarly, the algorithm uses two vehicle movements in even timesteps. However, the hindsight-optimal solution would merely satisfy the demand, with one movement from A to B in odd timesteps and one from B to A in even timesteps. Thus, the algorithm can lead to a loss of 2 versus the hindsight optimum. The example illustrates the core tradeoff: balancing can double the cost in a given time period, but ensures a state that is robust to future demand.

Figure 4 Wastefulness of Algorithm 1

In fact, Theorem 2 shows that this example is a worst-case outcome as the planning horizon grows longer. Specifically, Algorithm 1 is asymptotically 2-competitive against the hindsight-optimal solution. The hindsight-optimal benchmark observes the entire demand sequence D^1, \dots, D^τ in advance and jointly optimizes all routing decisions over the full time horizon. We use this benchmark to measure the cost of online decision-making under uncertainty. Due to having access to the demand from all time periods, the hindsight-optimal benchmark is able to provide a solution of no greater cost than any algorithm without prior access to future demand.

THEOREM 2. *Fix any inputs G, C , and S^0 . For any $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists τ_0 such that for any $\tau \geq \tau_0$, D^1, \dots, D^τ , the solution of Algorithm 1 satisfies the following, where $h^1, h^2, h^3, \dots, h^\tau$ is the hindsight-optimal solution:*

$$\sum_{t=0}^{\tau} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} x_{ij}^t < (2 + \varepsilon) \cdot \sum_{t=1}^{\tau} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} h_{ij}^t$$

The proof makes use of the following lemma, which shows that, for each timestep, the OffPDP-B induces a multiplicative loss of at most 2 relative to the hindsight-optimal solution. The proof of the theorem (in Appendix B.2) then merely shows that the price paid in the zero-th period to even out the vehicles becomes negligible as the planning horizon grows to infinity.

LEMMA 3. *Algorithm 1 is a 2-approximation of the hindsight-optimal solution at each timestep.*

Lemma 3 is proven by constructing a feasible solution to OffPDP-B whose cost is at most twice that of the hindsight solution in that period.

Therefore, the one-time balancing cost in period 0 becomes negligible over a long horizon, while each subsequent period costs at most twice the hindsight benchmark. As a result, the competitive ratio of Algorithm 1 converges to 2 as the planning horizon grows. This shows that Algorithm 1 is asymptotically 2-competitive. As noted in the earlier two-node example, this bound is tight.

4.2. Benchmark: A myopic baseline

Rather than solving OffPDP-B, a natural approach would be to merely solve the OffPDP at each timestep without constraining the ending locations of vehicles (Algorithm 2). This baseline is attractive because it fully optimizes for the current period, but this leads it to ignore the future value of vehicle positioning. This baseline would involve solving an NP-hard integer programming formulation at each timestep, as opposed to the polynomial network flow formulation from Section 3. Moreover, as shown in Theorem 3, this baseline can yield arbitrarily worse solutions than Algorithm 1 or than the hindsight-optimal solution.

Algorithm 2 Myopic baseline to solve OnPDP

Input: $G(V, E), C, S^0, D^1 \dots D^\tau$ where D^t is available at the start of timestep t

Initialization: Set $S^1 = S^0$

For $t = 1, \dots, \tau$, let x^t be an optimal solution to $PDP(G, S^t, -, C, D^t)$. Set S^{t+1} to the multiset of terminal nodes of the paths in x^t .

Return: x^1, \dots, x^τ

The next theorem shows that this benchmark can lead to bad solutions: short-sighted savings in one period can force very expensive repositioning in later periods.

THEOREM 3. For any $\kappa > 1$, there exists inputs G, C, S^0, τ_0 and D^1, D^2, \dots such that for any $\tau \geq \tau_0$:

$$\sum_{t=1}^{\tau} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} \gamma_{ij}^t > \kappa \cdot \sum_{t=0}^{\tau} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} x_{ij}^t$$

where x^1, \dots, x^τ and $\gamma^1, \dots, \gamma^\tau$ denote the solutions of Algorithms 1 and 2, respectively.

The proof is constructive (see illustration below or Appendix B.3 for details). We build instances in the Euclidean plane for which the ratio between the solution of the myopic algorithm and our online algorithm is larger than κ . At odd timesteps, a request appears from origin B to destination D . At even timesteps, a request appears from origin C to destination E .

Algorithm 1 begins by spreading out vehicles evenly, paying a fixed cost that Algorithm 2 does not. However, at any timestep, because there are vehicles at every node, Algorithm 1 merely involves using a vehicle to satisfy the demand and then returning it to its origin, causing a cost of only 2ϵ per timestep. As the number of timesteps grows large, the fixed cost becomes an arbitrarily small part of the total cost, showing how Algorithm 1 outperforms Algorithm 2 in this case.

Using Algorithm 2, odd-indexed steps start with a single vehicle at E and four vehicles at A . To satisfy the demand from B to D for these odd timesteps, the shortest possible solution would be to route the closest vehicle to B , where it can then go to D to fulfill the demand. As shown in Figure 6, this would therefore involve routing the vehicle from vertex E to vertex B and then to vertex D . This leaves a single vehicle at vertex D and four vehicles at vertex A before an even-indexed step. In even-indexed steps, we start with one vehicle at vertex D and four vehicles at vertex A . To fulfill the demand, the closest vehicle to vertex C (which would be the vehicle at vertex D) would be routed to vertex C and then to vertex E . As ε gets arbitrarily close to zero, this implies that the vast majority of the cost incurred is due to edges that are not directly used to satisfy demand.

This result shows the benefits of spreading vehicles evenly at each timestep. Recall that our online algorithm (Algorithm 1) pays a price at each timestep, by rebalancing vehicles evenly through the network at each timestep. As such, the online algorithm can incur a rebalancing cost of empty miles, but maintains an even distribution of vehicles at each timestep to better serve future demand. As Theorem 3 shows, the net effect can be positive and arbitrarily large, in that a myopic approach that ignores the impact of vehicles' ending locations on future operations can perform arbitrarily worse. In turn, this result shows the twofold benefits of Algorithm 1: (i) a reliance on an evenly distributed problem at each iteration, which is amenable to a polynomial network flow algorithm (Section 3); and (ii) a constraint that ensures a balanced distribution at each timestep, which can provide benefits in an online setting.

As a corollary, Algorithm 2 is not asymptotically c -competitive. Indeed, Algorithm 2 can perform arbitrarily worse than Algorithm 1, hence than the hindsight-optimal solution.

COROLLARY 1. *Algorithm 2 is not asymptotically c -competitive for any $c > 0$.*

In other words, solving each period optimally is not enough in this setting; solving each period in a way that preserves a good fleet state for the future is also important.

5. A strengthened online optimization procedure

We have shown in Section 3 and Section 4 that Algorithm 1 is computationally efficient—it solves a network flow at each timestep—and effective theoretically—it is asymptotically 2-competitive. However, in practice, the algorithm can lead to unnecessary empty miles. This is because Algorithm 1 restores a balanced state no matter what, even when some of the same movements could instead be absorbed into the next period's demand. Rather than spreading vehicles evenly at the end of each timestep, it would be more efficient to postpone rebalancing movements to the following timestep to serve future demand. In our earlier two-node example with alternating demand from A to B in odd timesteps and from B to A in even timesteps, postponing rebalancing movements would in fact eliminate all empty miles. We formalize this idea by maximizing the cost savings from unnecessary rebalancing and re-optimizing operations in the following timestep accordingly. We show that this algorithm still relies on network flow formulations and performs at least as well as Algorithm 1—hence, it is still polynomial and asymptotically 2-competitive.

5.1. Postponing rebalancing movements

In each of the m paths constituting an optimal solution to the OffPDP-B, we seek a two-part partition such that all demand gets covered in the first part and the second path merely involves rebalancing movements that can be postponed to the next timestep. This is formalized in the following definition.

DEFINITION 2. Consider disjoint paths P_1, P_2, \dots, P_m for one timestep of the problem. Let D denote the set of demand-covering edges, i.e., edges whose traversals are counted toward satisfying the realized demand in that timestep, and let $R := (\bigsqcup_{i=1}^m P_i) \setminus D$ denote the set of rebalancing edges,

i.e., edges traversed only to reposition vehicles. A set of *postponable rebalancing edges* $B_i \subseteq P_i$ satisfies (i) $B_i \subseteq P_i \cap R$, and (ii) edges in B_i occur after all edges in $P_i \setminus B_i$ in path P_i .

In other words, as seen in Figure 5.1, we split each path into an earlier segment that already serves all demand and a later segment consisting only of rebalancing movements. Rather than blindly traveling those "remainder" rebalancing edges at the start of the sequence in the following timestep, we can hope to optimize over those remainder edges along with the demand from the following timestep in hope that they may be used to improve the following day's solution.

Figure 7 Partitioning of an Eulerian tour into paths (colors), each one being split into a subpath excluding the last edge (curly arrows) and the last rebalancing edge (straight arrows), which corresponds to the highest-cost rebalancing edge into each node and which can be postponed to the following timestep.

Among all feasible splittings of the paths, it is natural in the online setting to postpone the rebalancing edges with the largest total cost, since these are the empty-mile movements we would most like to avoid. Due to the strict triangle inequality, we can assume without loss of generality that, on each path P_i , the rebalancing sequence in B_i involves at most one edge. Therefore, all rebalancing edges form a directed bipartite graph.

An upper bound for the cost savings is the sum of the costs of the longest incoming rebalancing edges in each node. Theorem 4 shows that this upper bound is tight and attainable, meaning that we can order edges in a way that the longest incoming rebalancing edge in each node appears last in a path—and can therefore be postponed to the following timestep.

THEOREM 4. *From any OffPDP-B solution, we can reconstruct feasible paths in the OffPDP-B such that the longest rebalancing edge ending at each node is the last edge in one of the paths. Therefore, these rebalancing edges form the set of postponable rebalancing edges of maximum cost.*

This theorem makes use of the following lemma, which shows that the network flow solution for OffPDP-B (including demand edges) can be partitioned into paths such that the largest rebalancing edge ending at each node appears last. We then split the paths into $P_i \setminus B_i$ and B_i to complete the theorem (Figure 7).

LEMMA 4. *Consider an n -node graph. Let E be a disjoint union of Eulerian tours, and $B \subseteq E$ such that at most one edge in B ends at each node. There exists a partition of the Eulerian tours into n paths with unique starting and ending points, such that each edge in B appears last in a path.*

5.2. Handling postponed edges

Next, we leverage those delayed rebalancing movements to serve demand in the following timestep, with the objective of turning them into demand-serving movements and therefore alleviating empty miles in the OnPDP solution. The constructive proof of Lemma 4 suggests that a modified version of Formulation (1) can be used to solve the case where vehicles do not all start at unique nodes but are constrained to end at unique nodes. Specifically, we define a modified network flow formulation

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} \cdot x_{ij} \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{j \in V} x_{ji} - \sum_{j \in V} x_{ij} = Q_i + 1 - \lambda_i, \quad \forall i \in V \\ & x_{ij} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where λ_i is the number of vehicles that start in node $i \in V$. The next result shows that this formulation can solve the offline PDP problem from any starting state to an even vehicle distribution.

THEOREM 5. *The optimum of $PDP(G, S, \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, C, D)$ can be derived from Problem (2).*

To sketch the idea behind this result, consider an optimal solution of Formulation (2) and add artificial edges corresponding to a bipartite matching from an even distribution to the starting state S . This creates Eulerian tours on each connected component, with at most one artificial edge beginning at each node.

We can then apply Lemma 4 to these Eulerian tours after reversing the tours (equivalently, by flipping the edge order). This yields a splitting in which the artificial edges appear first in each path. Removing those artificial edges then gives an optimal solution to $PDP(G, S, \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, C, D)$.

5.3. Postponing edges online

At this point, we have shown that we can postpone maximal-cost rebalancing edges to the following timestep from the OffPDP-B solution (Section 5.1) and that we can still use a network flow formulation to solve the subsequent problem from the resulting starting state to a balanced distribution (Section 5.2). To apply this procedure online, it remains to show that the resulting paths can still be split into (i) artificial rebalancing edges appearing first; (ii) demand-serving movements; and (iii) maximum-cost rebalancing edges appearing last (see Definition 3).

The main difference with the proof of Theorem 4 is that the upper bound formed by the largest rebalancing edges into each node can no longer be reached. Indeed, a connected component may have demand to serve but no vehicle at the beginning of a timestep, and may be such that all incoming edges are postponed rebalancing edges. Consider the following example in Figure 8:

Figure 8 Example network flow solution: demand edges red, postponed edges blue, artificial edges green.

The demand edges are marked in red, and the timestep starts with two vehicles each at nodes D , E , and F . The artificial edges from C to F , B to E , and A to D indicate possible edges that could be

traversed from the state of having one vehicle at each node to the actual start state for the timestep. In this case, this corresponds to having two vehicles on each of nodes D , E , and F . Here, not all of the longest rebalancing edges arriving at each node can be postponed until the following timestep. If all three of the rebalancing edges from F to C , E to B , and D to A were to be postponed to the following timestep, then the demand edges between vertices A , B , and C would have to somehow have been traversed while all the vehicles were at vertices D , E , and F .

Therefore, we design a subroutine that first attempts to postpone the maximal-cost rebalancing edge into each node and then, for each problematic connected component, removes the least-cost incoming rebalancing edge. Theorem 6 extends Theorem 4 by showing that this subroutine yields the set of rebalancing edges with maximum total cost that can be postponed to the next timestep.

DEFINITION 3. Consider disjoint paths P_1, P_2, \dots, P_m , partitioned into artificial edges A , rebalancing edges R and demand-covering edges D . A set of *postponable online rebalancing edges* $B_i \subseteq E$ satisfies (i) $B_i \subseteq P_i \cap R$, (ii) edges in B_i occur after edges in $P_i \setminus B_i$ in path P_i , and (iii) edges in $P_i \cap A$ occur before edges in $P_i \setminus (P_i \cap A)$ in path P_i .

Subroutine A Procedure to find the maximal-cost set of postponable rebalancing edges

Input: network flow solution corresponding to $PDP(G, S, \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, C, D)$. Let Y be the graph with node set V and edges in that solution.

Initialization: Find a minimum-cost bipartite matching from S to $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$; append these artificial edges a_i to Y to form Eulerian tours. Create a copy of Y , called \hat{Y} . Denote the set of maximal-cost (among all rebalancing edges going to the same node) rebalancing edges by B . Create empty node set Z .

For each node $j \in V$: if $\exists(j, v) \in A$ and $\exists(u, j) \in B$, then (i) replace the edges (j, v) and (u, j) in \hat{Y} with (u, v) , and (ii) add j to Z . If $u = v$, then remove the edge (u, v) from \hat{Y} .

For each connected component $H \subset \hat{Y}$ with more than one vertex: if the nodes of H are all in Z , then remove the edge of least cost in B that leads to a vertex in H .

Return: The resulting set B .

Subroutine A first attempts to postpone the largest-cost rebalancing edge arriving at each node. It then identifies connected subsets H of vertices that contain demand edges, but that would start the timestep with no vehicles and would receive no vehicles during the timestep if all candidate postponed edges into H were removed. Such a configuration cannot correspond to a feasible OffPDP solution, because the internal demand in H could not be served. Subroutine A would then enforce that one of the edges leading to H is not designated as a postponable rebalancing edge.

Figure 9 Illustration of Subroutine A.

Subroutine A is illustrated in Figure 9. Each of the connected components that ends up having an edge removed corresponds to a set of vertices that start with no vehicles because nodes in Z all have outgoing artificial edges in Y . Unless one of the edges going to that component is not postponed, there would be no vehicles in the component during the entire timestep, which would make it impossible to serve internal demand within H . As shown in the example, we choose the lowest-cost edge that we were trying to postpone and use it to satisfy the demand in the component. This allows us to fully satisfy demand, while postponing the maximum-cost set of rebalancing edges (as shown in Theorem 6).

THEOREM 6. *Subroutine A returns postponable online rebalancing edges of maximum cost.*

The proof examines the connected components identified in the last for loop of Subroutine A. Such a component contains demand but, after removing artificial edges and candidate postponed rebalancing edges, has no vehicle entering it during the timestep. Therefore, at least one incoming rebalancing edge into that component must remain in the current timestep. Subroutine A removes the least-cost such edge, which preserves feasibility while retaining the maximum possible postponed cost.

This result leads to Algorithm 3 to solve the OnPDP. As in Algorithm 1, the algorithm leverages a network flow formulation at each timestep (Theorem 5). The difference is that, at the end of each timestep, it postpones rebalancing edges with the largest costs while still serving all the demand (Theorem 6). In particular, Subroutine A is a polynomial algorithm, and so is Algorithm 3.

Algorithm 3 Strengthened online algorithm to solve OnPDP

Input: $G(V, E), C, S^0, D^1 \dots D^\tau$ where D^t is available at the start of timestep t

Initialization: Set $S^1 = S^0$

For $t = 1, \dots, \tau$: Let \tilde{x}^t be the network flow solution to $PDP(G, S^t, \{1, \dots, n\}, C, D^t)$. Get edges B^t from Subroutine A. Let $x^t = \tilde{x}^t - b^t, S^{t+1} := \{1, \dots, n\} - \{j | b_{ij}^t = 1\} + \{i | b_{ij}^t = 1\}$.

Return: x^1, \dots, x^τ

Let us illustrate Algorithm 3 in the example from Figure 5. In the first step, the optimal solution spreads one vehicle to each vertex while satisfying demand, by sending one vehicle from A to C , one vehicle from A to E , and two vehicles from A to B , one of which then continues on to satisfy the demand from B to D . However, the (A, C) edge, the (A, E) edge and one (A, B) edge can be postponed to the following timestep. In all other timesteps, Algorithm 3 mirrors Algorithm 1, although they do not start with one vehicle at each node. For example, in the second timestep, Algorithm 3 would move one vehicle from A to C , one from A to B , one from E to C , and the edge used to satisfy demand from C to E . The first two edges can be postponed to the third timestep, leaving just the edges pictured from C to E and E to C . All following timesteps are similar. In this example, Algorithm 3 is strictly more efficient than Algorithm 1 because it batches rebalancing decisions more effectively within the first timestep, leading to less empty-miles rebalancing. Subsequently, empty-miles rebalancing edges are avoided and optimized over in the following timestep. This implies that Subroutine A returns the set of postponable online rebalancing edges of largest possible cost.

Figure 10 Illustration of steps in Algorithm 3, demand in red

Algorithm 3 alleviates empty-mile rebalancing movements from Algorithm 1. As expected, it returns a solution that is at least as good. This is proved in Theorem 7 by induction.

THEOREM 7. Algorithm 3 returns a solution with a cost no greater than that of Algorithm 1.

COROLLARY 2. Algorithm 3 is asymptotically 2-competitive.

COROLLARY 3. (Algorithm 2 vs Algorithm 3 Cost Ratio is Unbounded) For any $\kappa > 0$, there exists OnPDP inputs such that Algorithm 2 outputs $\gamma^1, \gamma^2, \dots, \gamma^t$ and Algorithm 3 outputs network flow solutions s^1, s^2, \dots, s^t and edges to be delayed q^1, q^2, \dots, q^t such that $\frac{\sum_{k \geq 1, i, j \in V} c_{ij} \gamma_{ij}^k}{\sum_{k \geq 1, i, j \in V} c_{ij} s_{ij}^k - \sum_{k \geq 1, i, j \in V} c_{ij} q_{ij}^k} > \kappa$.

Figure 4 shows an example where the asymptotic bound of 2 is tight for Algorithm 1 but not for Algorithm 3. It remains open whether Algorithm 3 is asymptotically c -competitive for $c < 2$.

6. Computational results

We conclude with experiments to evaluate the network flow formulation of OffPDP-B against integer programming benchmarks, and to evaluate Algorithms 1 and 3 against the myopic baseline in Algorithm 2. Note that the integer programming benchmarks require subtour elimination constraints that allow subtours (which can be necessary to serve demand) but avoid disconnected cycles. We consider both a time-space network formulation (Jacquillat et al. 2022) and an integer programming formulation with copies of pickup and dropoff nodes (Savelsbergh and Sol 1995). Both benchmarks and the experimental setup are described in the remainder of this section.

6.1. Integer Programming formulations

Let x_{ij} be decision variables corresponding to the number of times any vehicle travels from i to j ; z_{kij} be decision variables corresponding to the number of times vehicle k travels from i to j ; and γ_{ki} be binary decision variables indicating whether vehicle k ends at location i . We denote by $t_*(i)$ the number of times i appears in multiset T .

We can model the OffPDP problem via the following integer programming formulation:

$$\min \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} x_{ij} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{s.t. } x_{ij} \geq d_{ij} \quad \forall i \neq j \in V \quad (4)$$

$$x_{ij} = \sum_{k \in [m]} z_{kij} \quad \forall i \neq j \in V \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V} z_{kij} - \sum_{j \in V} z_{kji} = -\gamma_{ki} \quad \forall k \in [m], i \in V \setminus \{s_k\} \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V} z_{kij} - \sum_{j \in V} z_{kji} = 1 - \gamma_{ki} \quad \forall k \in [m], i = s_k \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{i \in V} \gamma_{ki} = 1 \quad \forall k \in [m] \quad (8)$$

$$\bigcup_{i,j} z_{kij} \text{ is weakly connected} \quad \forall k \in [m] \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_k \gamma_{ki} = t_*(i) \quad \forall i \in V \quad (10)$$

$$x_{ij} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \quad \forall (i,j) \in E \quad (11)$$

$$z_{kij} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \quad \forall k \in [m], (i,j) \in E \quad (12)$$

$$\gamma_{ki} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall k \in [m], i \in V \quad (13)$$

Equation (3) minimizes total costs. Constraint (4) makes sure that demand is satisfied due to the triangle inequality, and the resulting assumption that vehicles travel directly from pickup to dropoff destinations. Constraint (5) is the linking constraint between the x and z variables. Constraints (6)-(8) ensure flow balance, so that each vehicle begins in its starting location and ends in its ending location. In Constraint (9), connectedness can be imposed via multiple methods, such as

using a time-space formulation or making copies of the pickup and dropoff location for each unit of delivery and then using generic subtour elimination constraints. Constraint (10) enforces that the vehicle ending locations match T , and can be ignored when solving $PDP(G, S, -, C, D)$.

Note that using generic subtour elimination constraints without duplicating nodes would overly constrain the problem, as vehicles may need to form tours if necessary to serve demand—as long as these subtours are not disconnected from the rest of the path. There are two subtour elimination methods used as benchmarks in Section 6 that avoid this issue.

The first method involves a time-space network (Jacquillat et al. 2022) to ensure that each vehicle takes a valid path over time. This can be formulated by removing constraints (5), (6), (7), (9), and (12), and adding the following constraints:

$$x_{ij} = \sum_{k \in [m]} \sum_{t=0}^{K-1} z_{kijt} \quad \forall i \neq j \in V \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V} z_{kij0} = \mathbb{1}_{\{i=s_k\}} \quad \forall k \in [m], i \in V \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V} z_{kji(K-1)} = \gamma_{ki} \quad \forall k \in [m], i \in V \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V} z_{kji(t-1)} - \sum_{j \in V} z_{kijt} = 0 \quad \forall k \in [m], i \in V, t \in \{1, \dots, K-1\} \quad (17)$$

$$z_{kijt} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall k \in [m], (i, j) \in E, t \in \{0, \dots, K-1\} \quad (18)$$

The time-space formulation utilizes an additional set of binary decision variables z_{kijt} , which equal 1 if vehicle k traverses the arc from node i to node j departing at "time" (in the time-space network) t , and 0 otherwise. Constraint (14) links the z variables to the x variables. Constraint (15) and Constraint (16) ensure that vehicles start and end at the correct nodes. Constraint (17) enforces flow balance.

K is the number of time-blocks. Specifically, the number of time-blocks represents the maximum length allowed for any vehicle's path. The model provides an exact representation given a large enough number of time blocks, leading to extensive computational requirements.

The second method involves making copies of nodes for the pickups and dropoffs of each node (Savelsbergh and Sol 1995).

First, split the demand matrix D into a set of transportation requests \mathcal{R} by taking each unit of demand from i to j as a unique request. For every request $r \in \mathcal{R}$, we generate two distinct logical nodes: a pickup node q_r located at the origin of the request, and a delivery node u_r located at the destination. We define Q as the set of all pickup nodes and U as the set of all delivery nodes.

To enforce the vehicle ending locations, we create a set of destination nodes $W = \{w_v \mid v \in V\}$, where each w_v is a logical clone of the physical node v . The complete set of nodes for the problem is $V' = Q \cup U \cup \{s_1, \dots, s_m\} \cup W$.

$$\min \sum_{k \in [m]} \sum_{(i,j) \in E'} c_{ij} x_{kij} \quad (19)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{k \in [m]} x_{kq_r u_r} = 1 \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (20)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V'} x_{kskj} = 1 \quad \forall k \in [m] \quad (21)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V'} x_{kzij} = 0 \quad \forall i \neq k \in [m] \quad (22)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V'} x_{kjsi} = 0 \quad \forall i, k \in [m] \quad (23)$$

$$\sum_{w_v \in W} \sum_{i \in V'} x_{kiw_v} = 1 \quad \forall k \in [m] \quad (24)$$

$$\sum_{w_v \in W} \sum_{i \in V'} x_{kw_v i} = 0 \quad \forall k \in [m] \quad (25)$$

$$\sum_{j \in Q \cup U} (x_{kij} - x_{kji}) = 0 \quad \forall k \in [m], i \in V' \quad (26)$$

$$\sum_{k \in [m]} \sum_{i \in V'} x_{kiw_v} = t_*(v) \quad \forall v \in V \quad (27)$$

$$\sum_{i, j \in S} x_{kij} \leq |S| - 1 \quad \forall k \in [m], S \subseteq Q \cup U, |S| \geq 2 \quad (28)$$

$$x_{kij} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall k \in [m], (i, j) \in E' \quad (29)$$

The binary decision variable x_{kij} takes the value 1 if vehicle k travels from logical node i to logical node j . Equation (19) minimizes the total travel cost across all vehicles. Constraint (20) ensures that every request r is served. Constraints (21), (22) and (23) govern the starting conditions, ensuring that every vehicle k departs from its specific starting node s_k exactly once and no vehicles go to s_k . Constraint (24) ensures that every vehicle completes its route by entering exactly one logical destination node w_v from the set of expanded destination nodes W . Constraint (25) ensures that no vehicles leave the destination nodes. Flow conservation through the request nodes is handled by Constraint (26). Constraint (27) enforces that the number of vehicles at v matches $t_*(v)$. Constraint (28) is a standard subtour elimination constraint.

By making every pickup and dropoff be at a distinct node, we remove the need to allow for any subtours at all, meaning that we can use generic subtour elimination constraints. This method, however, involves a larger network as well as an exponential number of subtour elimination constraints, necessitating row generation algorithms and also hindering tractability.

Here, there is a tradeoff between optimality and tractability: allowing for many time-blocks guarantees optimality, but is intractable to optimize over. Allowing for fewer time-blocks sacrifices optimality but reduces the solution space, potentially allowing for a faster solution output.

6.2. Experiments

6.2.1. Experimental setup We implemented the benchmarks and algorithms in Tables 1 and 2 in Julia 1.8.1 and solved integer programs with Gurobi 9.5.2 on a MacBook Pro 14 with a M1 Pro processor and 32GB of RAM.

Node locations were generated independently at random in a 1 unit by 1 unit square. Demands for each i, j pair were randomly generated i.i.d with average equal to the stated demand for the balanced demand. For the skewed demand experiments, demands for each i, j pair were randomly generated i.i.d with average equal to 1.25 times the stated demand for $i \geq j$ and generated i.i.d with average equal to 0.75 times the stated demand otherwise.

Because of the equivalence of the time-space and node duplication methods and the intractability of the latter, we only used the time-space method to benchmark against the network-flow algorithm in the online case.

In the online scenarios, each node/demand average pairing had random data generated with different timestep counts. While comparing across different node/demand average pairings should not be done due to the different timestep counts, each data sample was run with all three algorithms, so the purpose of Table 2 is to show the differences in runtimes and objective value across the different algorithms.

6.2.2. Experimental Results Table 1 reports results for the OffPDP-B problem, averaged over ten runs for each parameter values. As expected from Theorem 1, all formulations return the same solution. However, the network flow terminates several orders of magnitude faster than the two integer programming benchmarks on medium-sized instances—and scales much better to larger instances.

Table 1 Computational results for the OffPDP-B

Nodes	Demand	Flat Demand						Skewed demand					
		Runtime (ms)			Objective			Runtime (ms)			Objective		
		NF	TSN	ND	NF	TSN	ND	NF	TSN	ND	NF	TSN	ND
3	0.1	3.1	7.0	7.3	100	100	100	2.0	44.8	50.9	100	100	100
5	0.1	3.1	56.6	44.2	100	100	100	2.9	38.9	26.6	100	100	100
7	0.1	4.1	385.6	183.4	100	100	100	3.8	267.9	89.9	100	100	100
9	0.1	4.7	2117	786	100	100	100	4.1	1661	689.1	100	100	100
3	0.3	2.9	8.4	8.7	100	100	100	2.1	5.1	8.6	100	100	100
5	0.3	3.5	58.4	135.2	100	100	100	2.9	45.1	46.7	100	100	100
7	0.3	26.5	695.8	3022	100	100	100	3.2	429.5	2180	100	100	100
9	0.3	4.2	5291	95854	100	100	100	3.6	4237	108545	100	100	100
3	0.5	2.9	7.4	20.5	100	100	100	2.3	5.5	15.5	100	100	100
5	0.5	3.1	65.8	291.1	100	100	100	3.1	57.5	255.6	100	100	100
7	0.5	27.7	1456	317353	100	100	100	3.3	724.2	169998	100	100	100
9	0.5	4.4	13995	881764	100	100	100	3.9	10932	572443	100	100	100
3	0.7	2.4	7.5	21.7	100	100	100	2.3	6.2	12.8	100	100	100
5	0.7	3.6	108.4	5012	100	100	100	3.1	80.4	17267	100	100	100
7	0.7	4.2	1761	1.375e6	100	100	100	4.2	1596	1.115e6	100	100	100
9	0.7	5.6	31836	1.474e6	100	100	100	9.6	22974	751780	100	100	100

NF: network flow formulation; TSN: time-space network integer program; ND: node duplication integer program.
 Objective values normalized with respect to the exact integer programming solution.

Next, Table 2 reports results for small to medium instances of the OnPDP. All values are the average of 5 runs. As expected, Algorithm 3 returns higher-quality solutions than Algorithm 1, by up to 27%. This confirms the practical benefits of the postponing procedure to avoid unnecessary rebalancing empty miles. As compared to the myopic benchmark, Algorithm 3 performs consistently within 1-2%. However, Algorithm 3 terminates orders of magnitude faster than the myopic integer programming benchmark.

Table 2 Online algorithm runtime (in milliseconds) and objective value comparisons

Nodes	Demand	Flat Demand								Skewed demand							
		Runtime (ms)			Objective					Runtime (ms)			Objective				
		Alg. 1	Alg. 3	Alg. 2	Alg. 1	Alg. 3	Alg. 2	Diff. (%)	Alg. 1	Alg. 3	Alg. 2	Alg. 1	Alg. 3	Alg. 2	Diff. (%)		
3	0.2	1946	1847	10070	884	643	642	0.16	2092	1884	10990	1015	770	774	-0.52		
5	0.2	2441	2313	145143	3175	2609	2613	-0.15	3034	2673	153599	3032	2509	2510	-0.04		
7	0.2	573	584	496995	1066	916	899	1.89	440	439	235281	1074	933	929	0.43		
9	0.2	678	715	502978	1792	1571	1549	1.42	589	618	492547	1753	1556	1541	0.97		
11	0.2	223	257	741989	1126	1017	1000	1.70	232	259	881669	1056	963	953	1.05		
3	0.5	2078	1945	11224	2056	1718	1723	-0.29	2001	1879	10549	2391	2068	2081	-0.62		
5	0.5	2600	2489	155564	6411	5720	5705	0.26	2859	2673	178854	6610	6081	6105	-0.39		
7	0.5	537	565	680465	2492	2292	2284	0.35	435	431	748169	2290	2154	2153	0.05		
9	0.5	561	580	1.170e6	3794	3578	3564	0.39	586	616	1.426e6	4011	3837	3823	0.37		
11	0.5	247	268	6.302e6	2482	2359	2336	0.98	230	264	7.230e6	2609	2517	2496	0.84		
3	0.8	1964	1855	11883	2654	2409	2416	-0.29	1927	1770	12279	3037	2931	2943	-0.41		
5	0.8	2516	2428	180469	9555	8957	8950	0.08	2631	2414	218889	9645	9427	9430	-0.03		
7	0.8	530	542	1.44e6	3546	3388	3382	0.18	435	448	1.453e6	3619	3539	3534	0.14		
9	0.8	595	631	2.461e6	5915	5696	5663	0.58	593	614	2.746e6	6167	6069	6057	0.20		
11	0.8	271	281	1.360e7	4051	3934	3911	0.59	234	268	1.133e7	3946	3884	3864	0.52		
3	1.5	2083	2115	28348	5940	5407	5387	0.37	2062	1994	28730	7462	7360	7352	0.11		
5	1.5	2668	2688	1.040e6	18402	17495	17347	0.85	2841	2756	846824	23660	23499	23369	0.56		
7	1.5	593	622	1.309e6	6610	6387	6327	0.95	595	602	1.265e6	8476	8415	8371	0.53		
9	1.5	263	414	1.609e7	5094	4965	4898	1.37	606	638	3.003e7	15223	15155	15094	0.40		
3	2.5	2251	2199	51835	10015	9394	9345	0.52	2050	2033	46579	10255	10040	9989	0.51		
5	2.5	2821	2826	2.555e6	28588	27645	27449	0.71	3026	2751	2.106e6	32037	31733	31596	0.43		
7	2.5	613	729	4.887e6	11154	10918	10838	0.74	533	586	4.213e6	12318	12238	12183	0.45		
9	2.5	234	281	2.504e7	8139	8019	7958	0.77	276	315	1.903e7	9112	9071	9035	0.40		

“Diff.” measures the percent-wise difference between the solutions of Algorithms 2 and 3.

Algorithms 1 and 3 scale to large-scale problems for which Algorithm 2 fails to generate feasible solutions. In particular, we solved instances with up to 4,000 nodes in less than 40 minutes, whereas Algorithm 2 required one hour on instances with just 9 nodes. These results show the benefits of the polynomial network flow formulations at the core of our algorithms to solve the OnPDP.

7. Conclusion

In this paper, we studied the pickup and delivery problem in a high-vehicle regime and introduced a balanced offline variant in which the starting and ending vehicle locations cover all nodes. For this setting, we showed that the offline problem is equivalent to a network flow formulation, which yields a polynomial-time solution method.

We then used this balanced offline problem to develop polynomial-time algorithms for a new online pickup and delivery problem with batched demand, no backlog, and a cost-minimization objective. We showed that the resulting online algorithm is asymptotically 2-competitive, whereas a myopic integer-programming baseline is not c -competitive for any $c > 0$. We also developed a strengthened online procedure that reduces unnecessary empty-mile rebalancing in practice. Computational experiments showed that these methods return high-quality solutions at a small fraction of the runtime of integer-programming benchmarks. Together, these results show that preserving fleet coverage across locations is both computationally tractable and important for controlling long-run cost under uncertainty.

Several directions remain for future research. An important next step is to obtain stronger theoretical guarantees for Algorithm 3. Other potential directions include extending the model to probabilistic demand processes, time windows, heterogeneous fleets or other operational constraints. More broadly, the results suggest that balancing-based formulations could be a useful framework for a variety of other online routing and fleet-management problems under uncertainty.

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Appendix A: Appendix to Section 3

A.1. Proof of Lemma 1

Given an OffPDP-B solution $P := \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n\}$, let $H(P)$ denote the graph sum of the paths P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n . Let h_{ij} be the number of times an edge appears from vertex i to j in $H(P)$.

Consider the net flow difference $\sum_j h_{jk} - \sum_j h_{kj}$ for any node k . For each path defined as $P_i := (V_{i,1}, V_{i,2}, \dots, V_{i,n_i})$, the path P_i contributes to the sum as follows:

- +1 to the difference for the start node (i.e., $\sum_j h_{j, V_{i,1}} - \sum_j h_{V_{i,1}, j}$),
- -1 to the difference for the end node (i.e., $\sum_j h_{j, V_{i,n_i}} - \sum_j h_{V_{i,n_i}, j}$),
- 0 to the difference for any other node k in the graph where $k \neq V_{i,1}$ and $k \neq V_{i,n_i}$.

Summing across all P_i , and utilizing the fact that each vertex is the start node of exactly one path and the end node of exactly one path, we find that for all vertices k :

$$\sum_j h_{jk} - \sum_j h_{kj} = 1 + (-1) = 0.$$

By Claim 1, there must exist Eulerian tours on each connected component of the graph $H(P)$.

A.2. Proof of Lemma 2

Given an OffPDP-B solution $P := \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n\}$, let $H(P)$ denote the graph sum of the paths P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n . Let h_{ij} be the number of times an edge appears from vertex i to j in $H(P)$. Defining $x_{ij} := h_{ij} - d_{ij}$ for all i, j , we have for all $i \in V$, by the definition of Q_i and the proof of Lemma 1:

$$\sum_{j \in V} x_{ji} - \sum_{j \in V} x_{ij} = Q_i$$

. Furthermore, since P covers demand, we have $h_{ij} \geq d_{ij}$, implying $x_{ij} \in \mathbb{Z}_+$. Thus, any solution to OffPDP-B is feasible in Formulation (1).

Conversely, let x be a solution to Formulation (1). Define $y_{ij} := x_{ij} + d_{ij}$ for all i, j , and let Y be the multigraph with y_{ij} edges from node i to node j for all i, j . Observe that for all $i \in V$:

$$\sum_{j \in V} y_{ji} - \sum_{j \in V} y_{ij} = 0$$

so by Claim 1, each connected component of Y forms an Eulerian tour. Let $\{Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_K\}$ be the connected components of Y . For each component Y_k , let v_k be a vertex in Y_k and define P_k as the Eulerian tour of Y_k starting and ending at v_k . Assign empty paths for indices $j > k, j \leq n$. Then, $P := \{P_1, \dots, P_n\}$ is a feasible solution to OffPDP-B as each path has unique starting and ending vertices and P covers demand.

As any solution to Formulation (1) with objective value \tilde{C} would have cost $\tilde{C} + \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} d_{ij}$ in the OffPDP-B and any solution to OffPDP-B with cost \tilde{C} would have objective value $\tilde{C} - \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} d_{ij}$ in the above correspondence, any optimal solution in one problem would correspond to an optimal solution in the other.

A.3. Proof of Theorem 1

Formulation (1) gives a network flow formulation that solves OffPDP-B by Lemma 2.

Appendix B: Appendix to Section 4

B.1. Proof of Lemma 3

Let h_{ij}^t be the number of times edge (i, j) appears in the hindsight optimal solution for timestep t . Then, $x_{ij}^t := h_{ij}^t + h_{ji}^t - d_{ij}$ is a feasible solution for Formulation (1). The total cost of the corresponding OffPDP-B solution is:

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} (x_{ij}^t + d_{ij}) = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} (h_{ij}^t + h_{ji}^t) = 2 \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} h_{ij}^t$$

For optimal x^{*t} given by Algorithm 1, we know that the cost of x^{*t} is bounded by the cost of any feasible solution to OffPDP-B. Therefore:

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} x_{ij}^{*t} \leq \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} (x_{ij}^t + d_{ij}) = 2 \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} h_{ij}^t$$

B.2. Proof of Theorem 2

The following holds per Lemma 3:

$$\sum_{t=0}^{\tau} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} x_{ij}^t = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} x_{ij}^0 + \sum_{t=1}^{\tau} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} x_{ij}^t \leq \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} x_{ij}^0 + 2 \sum_{t=1}^{\tau} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} h_{ij}^t$$

Let \tilde{c} be the minimum edge cost in G . Since demand is non-zero at each timestep, we have $\sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} h_{ij}^t \geq \tilde{c}$ for all $t = 1, \dots, \tau$. Therefore:

$$\sum_{t=0}^{\tau} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} x_{ij}^t \leq \left(2 + \frac{\sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} x_{ij}^0}{\tau \tilde{c}} \right) \sum_{t=1}^{\tau} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} h_{ij}^t$$

Setting $\tau \geq \tau_0 := \frac{\sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij}}{\tilde{c} \varepsilon}$ gives the desired inequality.

B.3. Proof of Theorem 3

Consider five vertices A, B, C, D, E of coordinates $(0.5, 0), (0, 1), (1, 1), (0, 1 + \varepsilon)$, and $(1, 1 + \varepsilon)$ respectively in Euclidean space with arbitrarily small ε . Let there initially be four vehicles in A and one vehicle in E .

We consider an arbitrarily long time horizon τ . The demand stream consists of unit-load requests arriving sequentially. At odd timesteps, a request appears from origin B to destination D . At even timesteps, a request appears from origin C to destination E . Let the vertices be ordered $\{A, B, C, D, E\}$ corresponding to indices 1 through 5. The origin-destination demand matrix $\mathbf{D}^t \in \{0, 1\}^{5 \times 5}$ at timestep t is given by:

$$\mathbf{D}^t = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \text{if } t \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \text{ (Demand } B \rightarrow D), \\ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \text{if } t \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \text{ (Demand } C \rightarrow E). \end{cases}$$

Algorithm 1 outputs the following matching solution at the zero-th timestep

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Then, it outputs the following OffPDP-B solution

$$\begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \text{if } t \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \text{if } t \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \end{cases}$$

In comparison, Algorithm 2 outputs

$$\begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \text{if } t \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \text{if } t \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \end{cases}$$

Let x^1, \dots, x^τ and $\gamma^1, \dots, \gamma^\tau$ denote the solutions of Algorithms 1 and 2, respectively. Then

$$\sum_{t=1}^{\tau} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} \gamma_{ij}^t > \tau(1 + \varepsilon) > \kappa(3 + 2\tau\varepsilon) > \kappa \cdot \sum_{t=0}^{\tau} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} x_{ij}^t$$

where the middle inequality holds for $\varepsilon < \frac{0.1}{\kappa}, \tau \geq \tau_0 := 4\kappa$.

Appendix C: Appendix to Section 5

C.1. Proof of Lemma 4

Let u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k be the endpoints of the edges in B . Split up the Eulerian tours into paths where each path starts after one of the u_i by inserting breakpoints after each edge in B and then letting the paths be the edges between breakpoints. This is equivalent to having each path start at the end of an edge in B and end at the end of the next edge in B . Each path ends at some unique u_i , and therefore at a unique vertex. Similarly, each path starts some unique u_i , and therefore at some unique vertex. After adding empty paths starting and ending at each $v \in V \setminus \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k\}$, we obtain n paths with unique starting and ending points such that each edge in B appears last in a path.

C.2. Proof of Theorem 4

By Lemma 1, the edges of the OffPDP-B solution form an Eulerian tour on each connected component. Let B be the set containing the longest rebalancing edge ending at each node. By definition, at most one edge in B ends at each node. Thus, Lemma 4 partitions the edges of the OffPDP-B solution into n paths with unique starting and ending nodes such that the longest rebalancing edge ending at each node is the last edge in one of the paths. This implies that each edge in B is a postponable rebalancing edge. As any OffPDP-B solution has at most one path ending at each node, at most one rebalancing edge ending at each node can be postponable. Therefore, B forms the set of postponable rebalancing edges of maximum cost.

C.3. Proof of Theorem 5

The proof of Theorem 5 relies on the following claim:

CLAIM 2. *The degree balancing condition in Claim 1 remains invariant under the following operations: replacing a path $(u, w), (w, v)$ with a single edge (u, v) , reversing the direction of all edges, or contracting a set of vertices into a single vertex.*

Proof of Theorem 5: It is immediate that the graph sum of paths in any optimal solution of $PDP(G, S, \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, C, D)$ would be feasible in Formulation (2), so we must show the converse: that any solution in (2) decomposes into paths starting at S and ending at $\{1, \dots, n\}$. Consider the optimal solution x_{ij} in (2) and add a set of artificial edges, denoted by a_i , derived from a bipartite matching solution of $PDP(G, \{1, \dots, n\}, S, C, 0)$. Note that each a_i originates from a unique vertex by construction.

Next, we reverse the orientation of the graph, defining \hat{a}_i as the reversed artificial edges and $\hat{x}_{ij} = x_{ji}$. By Claim 1, the original variables satisfy the Eulerian tour criterion; therefore, by Claim 2, the reversed variables \hat{a}_i and \hat{x} do as well. Because the edges \hat{a}_i end at unique nodes, Lemma 4 implies that there exists a partition of the edges of $(\cup_i \hat{a}_i) \cup (\cup_{(i,j) \in E} \hat{x}_{ij})$ into n paths with unique starting and ending points, such that each edge in $\cup_i \hat{a}_i$ appears last in a path.

Finally, reversing these paths restores the original orientation, placing the a_i edges at the start. Removing these artificial edges yields a feasible solution for $PDP(G, S, \{1, \dots, n\}, D)$.

C.4. Proof of Theorem 6

The proof of this theorem relies on the following lemma:

LEMMA 5. *Each connected component H in \hat{Y} containing only vertices in Z contains exactly one rebalancing edge in Y leading to each of the nodes of H , and each of these edges comes from nodes outside of $V(H)$. In addition, each of these nodes has exactly one artificial edge in Y leading from it to $V(Y) \setminus V(H)$, and these artificial edges and rebalancing edges are the only edges between $V(H)$ and $V(Y) \setminus V(H)$.*

Proof of Lemma 5:

Consider a connected component H consisting solely of nodes in Z . First, we analyze the outgoing edges from $V(H)$ in Y . Every node in H corresponds to a vertex with an outgoing artificial edge in Y . These artificial edges must leave H and terminate in $V(Y) \setminus V(H)$. If an artificial edge were to terminate inside $V(H)$, it would create a path of two consecutive artificial edges, which is impossible in a min-cost bipartite matching. Furthermore, these are the only edges in Y directed from $V(H)$ to $V(Y) \setminus V(H)$, as the existence of any other edge would imply that H is connected to the rest of the graph in \hat{Y} , violating the definition of H as a component. Thus, there are exactly $|V(H)|$ edges directed from H to its complement in Y .

Next, we consider the incoming edges. Since there are $|V(H)|$ edges leaving H , there must be exactly $|V(H)|$ edges entering H from $V(Y) \setminus V(H)$. These incoming edges must be the edges replaced along with the $|V(H)|$ artificial edges in \hat{Y} ; otherwise, H would remain connected to $\hat{Y} \setminus H$. It follows from the node balance condition that every node in H receives exactly one rebalancing edge in Y originating from outside $V(H)$.

Finally, we show that there are no internal rebalancing edges within H . Suppose, for the sake of contradiction, that there is a rebalancing edge (i, j) where both $i, j \in V(H)$. From our previous step, we know there is also a rebalancing edge (w, i) entering H from some $w \in V(Y) \setminus V(H)$. This creates a path $w \rightarrow i \rightarrow j$. However, due to the strict inequality assumption of the costs and the optimality of the network flow solution, the path of edges (w, i) and (i, j) could be replaced by a single rebalancing edge (w, j) with strictly lower cost. This contradiction implies that no such internal edge (i, j) exists.

Proof of Theorem 6:

We first show that Subroutine A returns a set of postponable online rebalancing edges. Let $A = \{a_i\}$ be the set of artificial edges and $B = \{b_i\}$ be the set of rebalancing edges selected by the subroutine. We will partition the edges of Y into at most n paths with ending locations such that edges in A appear at the start and edges in B appear at the end, thereby showing that B is a set of postponable online rebalancing edges.

Decompose the edges of \hat{Y} into Eulerian tours for each connected component. Reversing the edge replacement procedure in Subroutine A ensures that for every vertex $i \in Z$, the artificial edge a_i immediately follows a rebalancing edge entering i . Note that this procedure possibly connects two connected components and therefore makes some Eulerian tours into non-Eulerian paths.

For each tour containing edges from A or B , introduce breakpoints immediately before each edge of A (at the tail of the a_i) and immediately after each edge in B (at the head of the b_i). This yields a collection of path segments where every a_i is a start edge and every b_i is an end edge.

As in Theorem 4, path endpoints are unique. Since every a_i originates at a unique vertex and every b_i terminates at a unique vertex, the only potential conflict is if a path ends at j (via b_k) and another starts at j (via a_k). However, by the edge replacement process, b_k and a_k are adjacent in the tour; thus, the path ending at b_k and the path starting at a_k are precisely the same path. Similar logic works to show the uniqueness of path starting points.

It remains to incorporate tours that contain no edges from A or B . Let \mathcal{E} be such a tour.

- *Case 1:* \mathcal{E} contains a vertex $v \notin Z$. This implies no artificial edge starts at v , or no rebalancing edge in B ends at v . If neither exist, we add a path covering \mathcal{E} that starts and ends at v . If only a b_k ends at v , we append \mathcal{E} into the path ending at v . If only an a_k starts at v , we append \mathcal{E} into the path starting at v .
- *Case 2:* \mathcal{E} belongs to a component H from Step 4. Here, a rebalancing edge ending at some node $u \in V(T)$ was explicitly excluded from B . Since $u \in Z$, there exists a corresponding a_k starting at u . Thus, there is a path ending at u into which we can append \mathcal{E} . Since no edge in B ends at u , this operation preserves the property that edges in B appear last.

Iteratively adding the tours that were not part of the paths to the set of paths, we can see that each time we add tours to the paths, we have not destroyed the uniqueness of the ending locations of the paths, and we have not destroyed the property of the a_i 's appearing first and the b_i 's appearing last. The uniqueness of the path ending locations implies that we have at most n such paths. Therefore, Subroutine A returns a set of postponable online rebalancing edges.

We now establish that the cost of the edges given by the Subroutine A is an upper bound on the cost of any set of postponable online rebalancing edges. Consider a connected component H consisting of nodes in Z identified in

Subroutine A. By Lemma 5, each vertex in H possesses exactly one rebalancing edge entering from $V(Y) \setminus V(H)$ and one artificial edge exiting to $V(Y) \setminus V(H)$, with no other edges traversing the cut between $V(H)$ and $V(Y) \setminus V(H)$.

For any valid solution to $PDP(G, S, (1, \dots, n), D)$, not all rebalancing edges entering $V(H)$ can be postponable online rebalancing edges. Since H is connected and $|V(H)| \geq 2$, there exist edges internal to H . If the solution paths have artificial edges at the beginning, the internal edges of H can only be covered after traversing an edge entering H . This implies that at least one rebalancing edge entering $V(H)$ must be traversed prior to the internal edges and thus cannot be the final edge in a path. Therefore, the maximum cost associated with postponable online rebalancing edges entering $V(H)$ is the total cost of these edges minus the cost of the cheapest one.

Since disjoint connected components share no vertices, the total cost of a set of postponable online rebalancing edges is bounded by the sum of these maximum costs across all such components H , plus the cost of the highest cost rebalancing edge entering each node not belonging to such a component. This implies that the cost of the edges given by Subroutine A is an upper bound on the cost of any set of postponable online rebalancing edges.

C.5. Proof of Theorem 7

Let $C(\alpha_t)$ denote the cumulative cost of Algorithm 1 after the t -th timestep. Let $C(\beta_t)$ denote the cumulative cost of Algorithm 3 after the t -th timestep, including the cost of edges that would be postponed until timestep $t + 1$. Let $C(q_t)$ be the cost of the edges postponed from the t -th step to the $(t + 1)$ -th step in Algorithm 3. Let $C(x_t)$ and $C(y_t)$ be the costs generated by the network flow linear program for Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 3, respectively, for the t -th timestep. Let q_t, x_t, y_t represent the corresponding multigraphs, and x_0 be the matching solution in Algorithm 1. We proceed by induction on t to show that $C(\beta_t) \leq C(\alpha_t)$ for all t .

Base Case: Consider $t = 1$. $x_0 + x_1$ constitutes a feasible solution for the linear program that yields y_1 . Thus, $C(\beta_1) \leq C(\alpha_1)$.

Inductive Step: Assume $C(\beta_t) \leq C(\alpha_t)$. We now assess $C(\beta_{t+1})$ and $C(\alpha_{t+1})$. By definition of $C(\beta_{t+1})$:

$$C(\beta_{t+1}) = C(\beta_t) - C(q_t) + C(y_{t+1})$$

. Because the sum of q_t and x_{t+1} represents a feasible solution to the linear program that outputs y_{t+1} :

$$C(y_{t+1}) \leq C(q_t) + C(x_{t+1})$$

Combining the last two inequalities:

$$C(\beta_{t+1}) \leq C(\beta_t) + C(x_{t+1})$$

By the inductive hypothesis, $C(\beta_t) \leq C(\alpha_t)$. Furthermore, by definition, $C(\alpha_{t+1}) = C(\alpha_t) + C(x_{t+1})$. Therefore:

$$C(\beta_{t+1}) \leq C(\alpha_t) + C(x_{t+1}) = C(\alpha_{t+1})$$

This completes the inductive step. Thus, $C(\beta_t) \leq C(\alpha_t)$ for all t .

Appendix D: Extension to the case with more vehicles than nodes: $m > n$

In this appendix we describe the natural extension of Algorithm 3 to the case where $m > n$. All formulations, algorithms, subroutines, and theorems in this section are direct generalizations of the $m = n$ case, and the proofs are effectively the exact same. In particular, when restricting to $m = n$, we obtain the results from Section 5.

The following is the natural analog of Formulation (2):

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} \cdot x_{ij} \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{j \in V} x_{ji} - \sum_{j \in V} x_{ij} \geq Q_i + 1 - \lambda_i, \quad \forall i \in V \\ & x_{ij} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Solving this network flow gives a solution to $PDP(G, S, T, C, D)$ of the lowest cost, where T is allowed to vary across all multisets of cardinality $|S|$ that contain $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

THEOREM 8. *The optimal solution of $\min_{\substack{T \supseteq \{1, \dots, n\}, |T|=|S|, \\ x \in PDP(G, S, T, C, D)}} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} x_{ij}$ can be derived from (30).*

The natural extension of Subroutine A is the following:

Subroutine B Procedure to find the maximal-cost set of postponable rebalancing edges: $m > n$

Input: network flow solution corresponding to $PDP(G, S, T, C, D)$, where $T \supseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $|T| = |S|$. Let Y be the graph with node set V and edges in that solution.

Initialization: Find a minimum-cost bipartite matching from T to S ; append these artificial edges a_i to Y to form Eulerian tours. Create a copy of Y , called \hat{Y} . Denote the set of $t_*(i)$ maximal-cost (among all rebalancing edges going to node i) rebalancing edges by B_i , where $t_*(i)$ is the number of occurrences of i in T . Let $B := \cup B_i$. Create empty node set Z . Let $\delta_i = 0$ for all $i \in V$.

While there exists $j \in V$ where $\exists(j, v) \in A$ and $\exists(u, j) \in B$: (i) replace the edges (j, v) and (u, j) in \hat{Y} with (u, v) , and (ii) add 1 to δ_j . If $u = v$, then remove the edge (u, v) from \hat{Y} .

For all $i \in V$, if $\delta_i = t_*(i)$, add i to Z .

For each connected component $H \subset \hat{Y}$ with more than one vertex: if the nodes of H are all in Z , then remove the edge of least cost in B that leads to a vertex in H .

Return: The resulting set B .

Subroutine B is similar to Subroutine A with the only major difference being that a node i is added to Z only when there are $t_*(i)$ many replaced paths of length 2 with i being the middle node. Subroutine B is able to find the maximal-cost set of postponable rebalancing edges within the network flow solution given by (30).

THEOREM 9. *Subroutine B returns postponable online rebalancing edges of maximum cost when $m \geq n$.*

Subroutine B then embeds into the following online algorithm to solve OnPDP when $m \geq n$:

Algorithm 4 Strengthened online algorithm to solve OnPDP: $m > n$

Input: $G(V, E), C, S^0, D^1 \dots D^\tau$ where D^t is available at the start of timestep t

Initialization: Set $S^1 = S^0$

For $t = 1, \dots, \tau$: Let \tilde{x}^t be the network flow solution corresponding to $PDP(G, S^t, T, C, D^t)$ obtained from adding demand and artificial edges to the solution of Formulation (30). Get rebalancing edges B^t from Subroutine B. Update $x^t = \tilde{x}^t - b^t$ and define $S^{t+1} := T$. Update S^{t+1} by removing $\sum_i b_{ij}^t$ copies of j for all $i \in V$ and adding $\sum_i b_{ji}^t$ copies of j for all $i \in V$.

Return: x^1, \dots, x^τ

Algorithm 4 has similar solution quality guarantees as that of Algorithm 3.

THEOREM 10. *Algorithm 4 is asymptotically 2-competitive.*